

Nano-Technology in Agriculture

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Introduction

Nanotechnology is a growing interdisciplinary science which connects knowledge of biology, chemistry, physics, engineering, and material science (Islam et al., 2009 and Miyazaki et al., 2009; Prasad et al., 2014). It utilizes nanoparticles in equipment and instruments of nanoscale dimensions. Nanoparticle are any material that has one or more dimension at the scale of 1 to 100 nm (Sekhon BS et al., 2014). Due to their small size and large surface area to volume ratio, they carry compounds like small molecular drugs, DNA, RNA, proteins and probes with higher efficiency (Albanese A. et al., 2012).

Nanotechnology has applications, such as production of energy, improve agriculture production, disease diagnosis, food processing and storage, resistance to pests and insects (Prasad et al., 2014, 2016, 2017). Nanotechnology supports agriculture and decrease environmental challenges by pesticide production, chemical fertilizers, and plant disease control by nanoparticles as environment friendly to improve the efficiency of pesticide with lower dose (Singh et al., 2014; Bhattacharyya et al., 2016). Agriculture comes second in the list of uses of nanotechnology by which tools can help to increase fertility of soil and crop yield. For example, small tools can be used to spray fertilizers at a regulated rate carefully. Also, nanoparticles could play an important role to increase detection power as diagnostic kits in plant disease control (Prasanna et al., 2007).

Nanotechnology has two important aspects: (a) synthesis of nanoscale compounds, and (b) application of this compound for the required objectives (Khan et al., 2014 and Rizvi et al., 2014). Nanotechnology has varied practices in disease management, the most common is application of nanoparticles in seeds and soil or leaves to protect plants from the pathogen or to control infection (Khan et al., 2014 and Rizvi et al., 2014). Nanoparticles suppress the pathogen in soil or plant parts. The physiochemical studies of nanoforms vary greatly, it makes possible to detect the impact of NPs on pathogen and use this technology in pathogen control (specially against bacterial and fungal pathogens).

Silver has antimicrobial properties and applied more comprehensively than any other inorganic antibacterial agent (Russell et al., 1994 and Hugo et al., 1994). Silver has been applied in pure form or compound form for many applications for its antimicrobial effect against pathogens but is nontoxic to humans (Yeo et al., 2003; Elchiguerra et al., 2005).

Various levels of inhibition effect on colony formation of *Bipolaris sorokiniana* and *Magnaporthe grisea* were shown by using silver compounds such as AgNO₃. It is seen that the colony formation decreased when concentrations of the silver compounds increased. The inhibition of colony formation was apparent within 1 h. Silver ions and nanoparticles significantly inhibited the colony and conidia formation of *Bipolaris sorokiniana* and *Magnaporthe grisea* respectively (Jo et al., 2009). *Raffaelea* sp. was significantly inhibited in a dose-dependent manner in the presence of silver nanoparticles (Kim et al., 2009). The silver nanoparticles showed the highest inhibition effect on germination growth of *S. sclerotiorum* compared with other fungi like *Rhizoctonia solani* and *S. minor* (Min et al., 2009).

Disinfectant activity of silver nanoparticles will increase by using silica-silver nanoparticles (Wainwright et al., 1986). Fungi which could be controlled by silica-silver are: *Blumeria* spp., *sphaerotheca* spp., *phytophthora* spp., *Rhizoctonia* spp., *colletotrichum* spp., *Botrytis* spp., *Magnaporthe* spp., and *Pythium* spp.

Mode of Action of AgNPs Against Microorganisms (Chaloupka et al., 2010.)

1. Interaction with cell wall and membrane (a) Changes in permeability (b) Disturbance in the administration of phosphates (c) Degradation of the plasma membrane (d) Collapse of the proton motive force (e) Inhibition of the ATP synthesis.
2. Influence on amino acids and enzymes (a) Bonding with amino acids (especially to –SH group) (b) Inhibition of enzyme activity with bonding to its active center.
3. Obstructions in energy recruitment (a) Influence on electron movement in the respiratory chain (b) Inhibition of cytochromes.
4. Impact on DNA and RNA (a) Breaks in hydrogen bonding (b) Inhibition of synthesis of nitrogen bases (c) Disorders of DNA and RNA synthesis (d) Denature ribosomes, inhibiting protein synthesis.
5. Generating reactive oxygen species (ROS).

Exposure of *Escherichia coli* to nano-ZnO showed loss in membrane integrity. Likewise, toxicity of NP of CuO and ZnO are connected with cell membrane damage (Heinlaan et al., 2008). The constructed biosensor in the isolate of *Pseudomonas putida* effectively and rapidly, within minutes, demonstrated dose-dependent toxicity of NP of Ag, CuO, and ZnO (Gajjar et al., 2009). In *Candida* spp the treated cells with Nano-Ag showed significant damage, which was characterized by the formation of a “pit” in their cell walls and pores in their plasma membrane (Lee J et al., 2010).

DNA damage of cells exposed to AgNP or ZnONP was evaluated through electrophoretic analysis in agarose gels. DNA fragmentation was not detected in DNA extracts from all microorganism treated with NPs (compared with DNA extracts from microorganisms not exposed to NPs). Ag ions inactivate proteins with SH groups and prevent the ability of DNA to replicate (Feng et al., 2000). Silver is known to alter cell membrane structure and functions. Silver also prevents the expression of proteins associated with ATP production (Yamanaka et al., 2005).

Conclusion

Globally, about 10% annual yield reduction in crops loss due to diseases, it often exceeds 20%, whereas in severe cases economic loss is caused to farmers globally. According to FAO reports, the diseases and pests are responsible for 25% crop loss. To combat this, new technologies are emerging, among them nanotechnology especially with nanoparticles application is an alternative to pesticides or assistant factor in preparation of pesticides (Martinelli et al., 2014). Nevertheless, nanomaterials may have side effects, and a risk assessment requires realization of their distribution in the food chain and environment.

Reference

1. Albanese A, Tang PS, Chan WC. 2012. The effect of nanoparticle size, shape, and surface chemistry on biological systems. *Annu. Rev. Biomed. Eng.* 14:1–16
2. Bhattacharyya A, Duraisamy P, Govindarajan M, Buhroo AA, Prasad R (2016) Nano-biofungicides: emerging trend in insect pest control. In: Prasad R (ed) *Advances and applications through fungal nanobiotechnology*. Springer International Publishing, Switzerland, pp 307–319
3. Chaloupka K, Malam Y, Seifalian AM (2010) Nanosilver as a new generation of nanoparticle in biomedical applications. *Trends Biotechnol* 28(11):580–588
4. Elchiguerra JL, Burt JL, Morones JR, Camacho Bragado A, Gao X, Lara HH, Yacaman MJ (2005) Interaction of silver nanoparticles with HIV-1. *J Nanobiotechnol* 3:6
5. Feng QL, Wu J, Chen GQ, Cui FZ, Kim TN, Kim JO (2000) A mechanistic study of the antibacterial effect of silver ions on *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *J Biomed Mater Res* 52(4):662–668
6. Gajjar P, Pettee B, Britt DW, Huang W, Johnson WP, Anderson AJ (2009) Antimicrobial activities of commercial nanoparticles against an environmental soil microbe, *Pseudomonas putida* KT2440. *J Biol Eng* 3:9. doi:10.1186/1754-1611-3-9
7. Heinlaan M, Ivask A, Blinova I, Dubourguier HC, Kahru A (2008) Toxicity of nanosized and bulk ZnO, CuO and TiO₂ to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* and crustaceans *Daphnia magna* and *Thamnocephalus platyurus*. *Chemosphere* 71(7):1308–1316
8. Islam N, Miyazaki K (2009) Nanotechnology innovation system: understanding hidden dynamics of nanoscience fusion trajectories. *Technol Forecast Soc Chang* 76:128–140
9. Jo Y, Kim K, Jung G (2009) Antifungal activity of silver ions and nanoparticles on phytopathogenic fungi. *Plant Dis* 93:1037–1043
10. Khan MR, Rizvi TF (2014) Nanotechnology: scope and application in plant disease management. *Plant Pathol J* 13(3):214–231
11. Kim SW, Kim KS, Lamsal K, Kim YJ, Kim SB, Jung M, Sim SJ, Kim HS, Chang SJ, Kim JK (2009) An in vitro study of the antifungal effect of silver nanoparticles on oak wilt pathogen *Raffaelea* sp. *J Microbiol Biotechnol* 19:760–764

12. Lee J, Kim KJ, Woo SS, Kim JG, Lee DG (2010) The silver nanoparticle (Nano-Ag): a new model for antifungal agents, silver nanoparticles. David Pozo Perez (ed), InTech. doi:10.5772/8510. Available at: <http://www.intechopen.com/books/silver-nanoparticles/the-silver-nanoparticlenano-ag-a-new-model-for-antifungal-agents>
13. Martinelli F, Scalenghe R, Davino S, Panno S, Scuderi G, Ruisi P, Villa P, Stroppiana D, Boschetti M, Goulart LR, Davis CE, Dandekar AM (2014) Advanced methods of plant disease detection:a review. *Agron Sustain Dev* 35:1–25
14. Min JS, Kim KS, Kim SW, Jung JH, Lamsal K, Kim SB, Jung M, Lee YS (2009) Effects of colloidal silver nanoparticles on sclerotium-forming phytopathogenic fungi. *Plant Pathol J* 25(4):376–380
15. Prasad R, Bhattacharyya A, Nguyen QD (2017) Nanotechnology in sustainable agriculture: recent developments, challenges, and perspectives. *Front Microbiol* 8:1014. doi:10.3389/ fmicb.2017.01014
16. Prasad R, Kumar V, Prasad KS (2014) Nanotechnology in sustainable agriculture: present concerns and future aspects. *Afr J Biotechnol* 13(6):705–713
17. Prasad R, Pandey R, Barman I (2016) Engineering tailored nanoparticles with microbes: quo vadis. *WIREs Nanomed Nanobiotechnol* 8:316–330. doi:10.1002/wnan.1363
18. Prasanna BM (2007) Nanotechnology in agriculture. ICAR National Fellow, Division of Genetics, IARI, New Delhi, pp 111–118
19. Russell AD, Hugo WB (1994) Antimicrobial activity and action of silver. *Prog Med Chem* 31:351–370
20. Sekhon BS. 2014. Nanotechnology in agri-food production: an overview. *Nanotechnol. Sci. Appl.* 7:31–53
21. Simgh S, Singh BK, Yadav SM, Gupta AK (2014) Applications of nanotechnology in agricultural and their role in disease management. *Res J Nanosci Nanotechnol.* doi:10.3923/rjnn.2014
22. Wainwright M, Grayston SJ, deJong P (1986) Adsorption of insoluble compounds by mycelium of the fungus *Mucor flavus*. *Enzym Microb Technol* 8:597–600
23. Yamanaka M, Hara K, Kudo J (2005) Bactericidal actions of a silver ion solution on *Escherichia coli*, studied by energy-filtering transmission electron microscopy and proteomic analysis. *Appl Environ Microbiol* 71:7589–7593
24. Yeo SY, Lee HJ, Jeong SH (2003) Preparation of nanocomposite fibers for permanent antibacterial effect. *J Mater Sci* 38:2143–2147.